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CLINIC OF PEPTIC ULCER OF THE STOMACH AND DUODENUM IN COMBINATION WITH IRRITABLE BOWEL SYNDROME

Resume.

The article presents the clinical features of irritable bowel syndrome against the background of peptic ulcer of the stomach (PUS) and duodenum (PUD). Peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum and irritable bowel syndrome are among the main diseases of the gastrointestinal tract. These pathologies remain a question of today, as wine is still relevant. The purpose of the study is to evaluate the clinical features of irritable bowel syndrome against the background of peptic ulcer. Research materials. All patients received inpatient treatment in the gastroenterology department of the Chernivtsi Regional Clinical Hospital in 2013-2016. Diagnosis was carried out in accordance with the National recommendations of the Unified clinical protocol of primary, emergency and secondary (specialized) medical care for patients with PUS and PUD in adults, approved by the order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine No. 613 of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine dated September 3, 2014. Research results. The analysis of the features of the clinical course of the disease showed that all patients infected with HP had a pain syndrome. The presence of pain was noted by 92.3% of patients with PUS, 85.7% of patients with PUD. And signs of dyspeptic syndrome were found in patients with PUS - in 84.6% of cases, and with PUD - in 100% of cases ($p < 0.05$). In all examined patients with PCOS, the dyspeptic syndrome prevailed, namely abdominal discomfort - 60% ($n=75$), grumbling - 36% ($n=39$), heaviness in the abdomen - 52% ($n=56$), loose loose stools - 33% ($n=35$), constipation - 32% ($n=34$). Pain syndrome was detected in 79 patients (65%)

Conclusion. Therefore, irritable bowel syndrome, which manifests itself as a pronounced dyspeptic syndrome, combined with peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum, aggravates the course of the main disease with an increase in pain and astheno-vegetative syndrome.

Keywords. Peptic ulcer, stomach, duodenum, irritable bowel syndrome.

Introduction. Peptic ulcer (PU) remains one of the most common nosological forms of modern gastroenterology (prevalence in Ukraine is 7-10) [7, 9, 11]. The role of *H. pylori* as an unconditional pathogen has long been convincingly proven. However, recently there have been reports of innate and acquired immune defenses of the host organism, which, together with the factors of the gastric environment, stimulate a high rate of genomic variability of *H. pylori* [8,11], which contributes to the active evolution of the pathogen and its adaptation to its host. The increased virulence of HP, determined by the genes *cagA* and *vacA*, leads to the development of the most serious diseases of the stomach and PUD: atrophic gastritis, peptic ulcer disease, and stomach cancer [10].

As you know, irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) is a functional bowel disease that manifests itself at a young working age, is associated with defecation or a change in the usual mode of bowel work, which leads to a violation of the act of defecation and occurs against the background of neuropsychiatric disorders, a disturbed diet, genetic predisposition or experienced acute intestinal infection [1,2,3,12]. PCOS is an urgent

problem due to the significant prevalence of the disease, a sharp decrease in the quality of life of patients, and large economic costs for treatment. IBS is defined as a complex of functional bowel disorders lasting more than 3 months [4, 5, 6].

Purpose: to evaluate the clinical features of irritable bowel syndrome against the background of peptic ulcer.

Materials and methods. All patients received inpatient treatment in the gastroenterology department of the Chernivtsi Regional Clinical Hospital in 2013-2016.

The presence of PUS and PUD was verified on the basis of the clinical picture, anamnesis data, objective methods of examining the patient, the results of endoscopic and morphological studies of stomach mucosa and duodenum mucosa. To assess the patients' complaints and the results of the objective examination, we used the indicator of average degree of severity (SST). To calculate this indicator, the intensity of pain and other manifestations of combined pathology were first assessed according to the scale: 0 points — no complaints; 1 point — complaints are minimal; 2 points

— complaints are moderate; 3 points — complaints are pronounced or very pronounced. After that, SST was calculated according to formula:

$$SST = \frac{a + 2b + 3c}{a + b + c + d}$$

where SST is the average degree of severity of clinical manifestations; a - the number of patients with symptom severity of 1 point; b - the number of patients with symptom severity of 2 points; c - the number of patients with symptom severity of 3 points; d - the number of patients with no symptom.

Diagnostics was carried out in accordance with the National recommendations of the Unified clinical protocol of primary, emergency and secondary (specialized) medical care for patients with PUS and

PUD in adults, approved by order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine No. 613 of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine dated September 3, 2014.

Inclusion criteria for the study: male and female patients over 18 years of age with verified peptic ulcer of the stomach and PPD associated with toxigenic (cagA, vacA) strains of *H. pylori*.

Patients under the age of 18 and over 75 years of age with HP-negative and complicated (perforation, penetration, bleeding, etc.) PUS and PUD were not included in the study.

Research results.

Table 1 presents the distribution of patients by age and gender.

Table 1

Distribution of examined patients by age and gender (n;%)

Age	PC and PD (n=53)	
	Men, n, %	Women, n, %
18-29 (n=7)	3 (75%)	1 (25%)
30-39 (n=28)	7 (77,78%)	2 (22,22%)
40-49 (n=40)	5 (41,47%)	7 (58,33%)
50-59 (n=60)	14 (56%)	11 (44%)
60-69 (n=9)	2 (66,67%)	1 (33,33%)
OLL	31 (58,49%)	22 (41,51%)

Fig. 1. Distribution of patients with peptic ulcer of the stomach depending on localization of the ulcer defect, %

The distribution of patients with PV depending on the size of the ulcer defect is shown in table. 2

In patients with PUS, a small-sized ulcer was observed in 18 patients (54.5%), medium-sized - in 13 (39.4%), large-sized - in 2 people (6.1%).

Table 2

Distribution of patients with peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum depending on the size of the ulcer, (number of people)

Disease	ulcer sizes		
	small ulcer	average ulcer	big ulcer
Peptic ulcer of the stomach	18 (54,5%)	13 (38,4%)	2 (6,1%)
Peptic ulcer of the duodenum	8 (40%)	10 (50%)	2 (10%)

In patients with PD, a small-sized ulcer occurred in 8 patients (40%), a medium-sized one in 10 patients (50%), and a large-sized one in 2 patients (10%).

The analysis of the features of the clinical course of the disease (Table 3) showed that all patients infected with HP had a pain syndrome. The presence of pain was

noted by 92.3% of patients with PVS, 85.7% of patients with PUD.

Table 3

Peculiarities of the clinical course of peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum %.

Clinical	Peptic ulcer of the stomach n= 30	Peptic ulcer of the duodenum n= 18
pain syndrome	17 (100%)	11 (100%)
localization:		
epigastrium	11 (64,7%)	3 (27,3%)
peri-umbilical zone	6 (35,3%)	3 (27,3%)
right rib cage	-	5 (45,4%)
nature of pain:		
aching, dull	10 (58,8%)	7 (63,6%)
barbed	4 (23,5%)	2 (18,2%)
cutting	3 (17,7%)	2 (18,2%)
Reduction pain after eating	12 (70,6%)	9 (81,8%)

It should also be noted that the clinical signs of dyspeptic syndrome are more often detected (PUS - in 84.6% of cases, PUD - in 100% of cases). This was mainly due to a relatively higher number of cases of appetite disturbance, nausea and belching. Regarding the manifestations of asthenovegetative syndrome (emotional lability and sweating), observation of

patients showed opposite results in patients with PUS and PUD ($p < 0.05$).

Evaluating the degrees of severity of clinical syndromes, it was established that the average degree of severity (SST) of the pain syndrome (Fig. 2) in patients with PVS was 1.59 points, and in PDK the indicated indicators were 1.55 points.

Fig. 2. Intensity of pain syndrome in patients with peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum, points.

The CST of the dyspeptic syndrome also depended on the toxigenicity of HP strains in patients with PV. The highest indicators of SST of this syndrome were

noted in all groups of patients: 1.23 points - in PUS and 1.43 points - in PUD ($p < 0.05$).

Fig. 3. Intensity of dyspeptic syndrome in patients for peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum, points

The highest SST indicators of astheno-vegetative syndrome (Fig. 4) reached 1.62 points and 1.83 points in patients with PUS and PUD.

Fig. 4 Intensity of astheno-vegetative syndrome in patients for peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum, points.

A careful analysis of the complaints of patients with irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) made it possible not only to identify manifestations of digestive disorders, but also to estimate their frequency among the examined patients. It should be noted that the detected clinical manifestations of damage to the digestive organs were multidirectional in nature. In all examined patients, the dyspeptic syndrome prevailed, namely, abdominal discomfort - 60% (n=75), grumbling - 36% (n=39), heaviness in the abdomen - 52% (n=56), loose loose stools - 33% (n=35), constipation - 32% (n=34). Pain syndrome was detected in 79 patients (65%)

Conclusion. Therefore, irritable bowel syndrome, which manifests itself as a pronounced dyspeptic syndrome, combined with peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum, aggravates the course of the main disease with an increase in pain and astheno-vegetative syndrome.

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